

FUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF POLYSEMY IN THE PROCESS OF TRANSLATION (UZBEK AND ENGLISH CONTEXTS)

Author: **Shonazarov Shahroz Baxronjonovich**

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7817416>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 02nd April 2023

Accepted: 10th April 2023

Online: 11th April 2023

KEY WORDS

Functional features, polisemantic words, translation of polisemantic terms, translation equivalent.

ABSTRACT

The present work is dedicated to the functional features of polysemy words and to the issue of translation of English polysemantic terms in different contexts. The paper presents the analysis of terms used in the literal translation. The objective of the research is to reveal the significance of correct and accurate rendering of terms for the effectiveness and accurate of intercultural professional communication. Particular attention in the paper is paid to the study of the meanings of literal terms listed in Uzbek and English languages. The authors conclude that functional features and correct translation of polysemy terms are complicated process and it should be done firstly understanding the functions of polysemy and secondly, the needs of dictionaries. Furthermore, different meanings of polysemy in contexts are analyzed in this paper.

Introduction

Polysemy is the singular form of the word that can be associated with several different meanings. It means that the polysemy is a word that has many meanings of relationship. The problems are often discovered by researchers and translators in translating words, sentences or phrases which contain of polysemy is when translators cannot get the exact meaning and when translators are not sure of the meaning to translate, especially when it comes to translation from the source language in to the target language. Thus, for translators to understand the message of the English text clearly which is in this case of the source text, they need to understand the meaning of words, especially keywords to translate them successfully to produce a coherent target text in Indonesian. In other words, translators sometimes find difficulty in finding the meaning of some polysemy words. Therefore, they fail most of the time in transmitting the message clearly because of the difficulty of the English words because it is a foreign language. The main object of translating polysemy is the meaning. When facing the text, the translator will find two elements: the reader and the writer. When the translator translates a text, then in this case the translator also conducts the interpretation of meaning.

Literature review

The mysterious world of words is an object of scientific investigation by Lyons J. (6, 1995; 376p). The phenomenon which a word has a set of meanings is called polysemy. Most of the words in the Uzbek and English languages are polysemantic that's why this issue has become an important sphere of semantics to investigate on it. Some people who are not well aware of linguistics suppose that if one word is applied on wide range of meanings, this language is lacking on vocabulary. In fact, it is exactly the opposite: if each word has at least two meanings, the expressiveness of the whole vocabulary increases twofold and it comes out that the emotive potential of the language is high and polysemy is a great advantage to a language.

The first time the term –polysemy appeared was in Michel Bréal's *Essai de Sémantique* (1897), later on translated into English under the name of *Semantics: Studies in the Science of Meaning* (1900) from *πολύς*, –numerous, and *σημειον*, –signification. (Bréal, 1900), from which the following excerpt, containing the newly coined term, is taken: –The new meaning of a word, whatever it may be, does not make an end of the old. The same term can be employed alternately in the strict or in the metaphorical sense, in the restricted or in the expanded sense, in the abstract or in the concrete sense. In proportion as a new signification is given to a word, it appears to multiply and produce fresh examples, similar in form, but differing in value. We shall call this phenomenon of multiplication *Polysemia*”

The first study was conducted by Bian and Chen, with the title of the research “Resolving Translation Ambiguity and Target Polysemy in CrossLanguage Information Retrieval.” 4 The result of this study based on experiments show that a gain performance of about 10.11% can be achieved in resolving both translation ambiguity and target polysemy compare to the method which performs translation disambiguation only in cross-language information retrieval based on analyzed two factors : word sense ambiguity in the source language (translation ambiguity), and word sense ambiguity on the target language (target polysemy). The second study was done by Nur 'Azizah with the title of the study “Polisemi Kata Wali dan Auliya dalam Al-Qur'an: Studi Kasus Terjemahan Hamka dan Quraish Shihab.” 5 The result of this study are Found the meaning of the word Auliya and wali, and proved that the meaning has more than one meaning. Found the meaning of wali and auliya from Hamka and Quraish Shihab. Found the similarities and differences between the guardian and the word auliya. The third study was done by John Old with the title of the research “Analysis of Polysemy and Homographs of the Word "lead" in Roget's International Thesaurus, 3rd Edition.” 6 The result of his study are the entries for lead (metal) as opposed to the entries for lead (precede, govern). The former is a mass noun while the latter is a primarily used to describe process (used as a verb). It seems that when the meaning of a mass noun (or perhaps all nouns) is extended (through metaphor, "borrowing" etc.) it tends to create new and different meanings, while extending process meanings "extends" that semantic space (the meaning) without partitioning it.

Research Questions

Considering the idea that has been presented in the background above, this study formulates the research questions as follows:

- 1. What are Polysemy Translation Strategies used in different contexts?***
- 2. What are the functional features of Polysemy in translation process?***

Furthermore, the significance of this paper is expected to be useful in translation field, to find strategy used in translating polysemy words and make the reader understand functional features of polysemy words.

Research Methodology

Method of the research paper is a qualitative descriptive method. Qualitative method is a method of data collection, data analysis, report writing and the overall patterns or shapes that are arranged in the research process. Basically, the qualitative approach aimed more towards the search for meanings, that is, the explanations and meanings people give to events, objects, other people, and situations in their environment and its focus in the nature of phenomena of human beings. This is the approach used in this study. This method also be guidance and reference in this study to collecting the data that are already collected and then applying this theory in it. First, this study collected data in the form of words from the source language that has polysemy meaning when translated into the target language. Second, this study gives a note on the data to be analyzed. Third, this study analyzed by using dictionaries, and other reference theory that are relevant to the translation of polysemantic words.

Research analysis

After finding specific words and terms which have polysemantic meanings from different contexts, in this section their analysis and translation in Uzbek and English languages are given. The words are analyzed based on their morphological and syntactic forms and functional features. For example, adjectives are used in many senses and they are context dependent and flexible. For example, "light" has only two meanings in Uzbek language. 1. yengil 2. yorug'. But we divide it into groups that express different meanings related to this quality: "a light rain" (shivirlab yog'gan yomg'ir), "her light voice" (uning mayin ovozi), "a light blue shirt" (och moviy rang fudbolka), "a light lunch" (yengil tamaddi), "the light breeze" (yengil shabada), "a light white wine" (kuchsiz oq vino), "a light sleep" (yengilgina uyqu), "light injures" (yengil jarohat) "light housework" (yengil uy ishlari). When thinking about an antonym, we should think about the situation in which it is used. For example, when the antonym of the adjective "light" becomes "dark", it should be separated from another antonym of "light", "heavy". How the adjectives are formed is also important, that is, their formation with the participation of nouns is the main analysis tool. These methods led to the creation of the "Cobuild Dictionary", which requires the classification of the meanings of ambiguous adjectives into types. Another way to distinguish the meaning between adjectives is to know what kind of part of speech it is. For example: My old girlfriend (attributive) and My girlfriend is old (predicative).

Other comparative examples of Uzbek and English polysemantic words with samples:

In English

GOLDEN HAIR - Besides Della has beautiful golden hair.

Golden: 1). having a bright yellow color like gold. 2). A golden opportunity – a good chance to get something valuable or to be very successful. 3). Golden boy/girl – someone who is popular and successful. 4). A golden period of time is one of great happiness or success: golden years, golden days.

As we see that, there are many meaning of –golden and author used the word to describe woman's hair.

In Uzbek –oltin (tilla) has many meanings –oltin soch, –oltin kalit, –tilla bola, –tilla fikr and we can also use the word –oltin to describe like this, and translate the sentence into Uzbek with equivalent.

Based on the result of the research, the writer found that there are polysemy words translation is depend on the contexts and the dictionary which the translator uses.

Conclusion

Terminology is an important area in any directions and contexts, and it requires great attention and consideration. Nowadays, linguists are paying greater attention to the issue of polysemy of terms in general, and to literal terms in particular as well as their functional features in translation. Consequently, adequate translation of literal terms becomes very important since it can prevent possible misunderstanding between the translator and the reader.

The correct translation of terms depends on certain factors that should be taken into consideration. These include:

- General characteristics and specific features of a term;
- The specificity of languages from which and into which the term is translated
- Word formats whether they are adjectives, nouns and etc.

The study has shown that the main problem is caused by misunderstanding of different meanings of terms and words since they are completely depend on the contexts, morphological formats and syntactical structure.

References:

1. Abdullah, A. (2013). Cognitive semantic Analysis of Polysemous Words in English, (Iraq : University Of Sulaimani-Sulaimani Faculty Of Humanities School Of Languages English Department).
2. Ahmanova, O.S. (1979). *Lingvistika i Semiotika [Linguistics and Semiotics]*. Moscow: Izd-vo MGU (in Russian).
3. Allan C. (2001). *Meaning in Language: An Introduction to Semantics and Pragmatics*, (Oxford University Press, Oxford).
4. Atkins C.J. (2000). *Describing Polysemy*. Oxford. Oxford University Press. 125 p4.
5. Buronov J. (1973). *Comparative grammar of English and Uzbek languages*. T. O'qituvchi. 138 p.
6. Cabré, T. (1999). *Terminology: Theory, Methods and Applications*. Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
7. Catford, J.C. (1978). *A Linguistic Theory of Translation. An Essay in Applied Linguistics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
8. Chesterman, A. (1997). *Memes of Translation: The Spread of Ideas in Translation Theory*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
9. Collins English Dictionary and Thesaurus, Version 1.0. (1992). New York: HarperCollins Publishers.
10. Hanks P. (1987). *Definitions and explanations*. Sinclair John. 1987 -136p.